

CAUSATION

International Journal of Science

Without cytomegalovirus infection, no unstable angina pectoris

Research article

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Impressum:

CAUSATION

International Journal Of Science

Chief-Editor / V. i. S. d. P.:

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Hegelitzer Str. 22

DE-26409 Wittmund-Ardorf (Germany)

© Editorial Team: **EDITORIAL TEAM**

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✉ E-Mail: editor@causation.eu

☎ Phone: +(49) 4466 - 333

Year: 2024; Volume: 19; Issue: 8; pp. 5–20.

✉ Received: April 16, 2023

✓ Accepted: April 16, 2023

📅 Published: April 16, 2023

📄 Deutsche Nationalbibliothek Frankfurt

🔗 ISSN: 1863-9542

DOI:10.5281/zenodo.7833017

🔍 Find in: [Zenodo](#) [Orcid](#) [Academia ...](#)

Abstract**BACKGROUND:**

The relationship between cytomegalovirus infection and unstable angina pectoris has been re-investigated.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

New statistical methods have been used.

RESULTS:

The data of the study of Alavi et al., 2011 (Iran) have been re-analysed.

CONCLUSION:

Without cytomegalovirus infection, no unstable angina pectoris.

Keywords:

Cytomegalovirus; Unstable angina pectoris; Cause; Effect; Causal relationship k; Causality; Causation

© Reviewer 1: None/Author.

© Reviewer 2: None.

© Reviewer 3: None.

1. Introduction

Atherosclerosis is widely recognized as an inflammatory ¹ disorder characterized by infiltration of macrophages and lymphocytes into the artery wall, endothelial dysfunction ² and increased smooth muscle ³ cell proliferation. Human cytomegalovirus (CMV), a ubiquitous pathogen or human herpesvirus-5 (HHV-5) that establishes a lifelong persistent infection, has long been proposed as a risk factor for atherosclerosis. The seroprevalence of CMV in the United States in children age 6 to 11 is about 37% and increases gradually to nearly 100% by the ninth decade of life ⁴ CMV represents a lifelong burden ⁵ of immune surveillance and immune dysfunction. Several publications pointed to the possibility that a human cytomegalovirus infection might contribute even to risk of coronary artery disease (CAD). However, relationship between CMV infection and CAD is still controversial.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Material

2.1.1. The study of Seyed Mohammad Alavi et al., 2011, Iran

Seyed Mohammad Alavi et al. ⁶ measured serum CMV Immunoglobulin G (IgG) levels in 96 cases and 96 controls in order to determine whether unstable angina (UA) according to American Heart Association Criteria is related to chronic cytomegalovirus infection. In toto, 90/96 of patients with unstable angina and 87/96 patients of the control group were CMV-IgG positive with sensitivity of 88% - 93% and specificity of 95%-98%. The necessary condition relationship between CMV IgG positive and unstable angina is calculated as $(1 - (6/(96+96))) = 0.96875$.

However, let us assume that all 96 cases were CMV IgG positive. The laboratory kit used could recognize a minimum rate of true positive (sensitivity) of $0.88 \times 96 = 84.48$ cases or a maximum rate of true positive (sensitivity) of $0.93 \times 96 = 89.28$ cases. The kit used could not recognize more than 90 cases, which were recognized.

¹Ross R. Atherosclerosis—an inflammatory disease. *N Engl J Med.* 1999 Jan 14;340(2):115-26. doi: 10.1056/NEJM199901143400207. PMID: 9887164.

²Gimbrone MA. The Gordon Wilson lecture. Understanding vascular endothelium: a pilgrim's progress. Endothelial dysfunction, biomechanical forces and the pathobiology of atherosclerosis. *Trans Am Clin Climatol Assoc.* 2010;121:115-27; discussion 127. PMID: 20697555; PMCID: PMC2917138.

³Raines EW, Ross R. Smooth muscle cells and the pathogenesis of the lesions of atherosclerosis. *Br Heart J.* 1993 Jan;69(1 Suppl):S30-7. doi: 10.1136/hrt.69.1.suppl.s30. PMID: 8427762; PMCID: PMC1025256.

⁴Bate SL, Dollard SC, Cannon MJ. Cytomegalovirus seroprevalence in the United States: the national health and nutrition examination surveys, 1988-2004. *Clin Infect Dis.* 2010 Jun 1;50(11):1439-47. doi: 10.1086/652438. PMID: 20426575.

⁵Gupta M, Shorman M. Cytomegalovirus. 2022 Aug 8. In: StatPearls [Internet]. Treasure Island (FL): StatPearls Publishing; 2023 Jan-. PMID: 29083720.

⁶Alavi SM, Adel SM, Rajabzadeh AR. An evidence against the effect of chronic cytomegalovirus infection in unstable angina pectoris. *Acta Med Iran.* 2011;49(2):78-80. PMID: 21598213.

Table 1. CMV IgG and UA (Study of Alavi et al., 2011, Iran).

		CAD		
		YES	NO	
CMV IgG	YES	90	87	177
	NO	6	9	15
		96	96	192

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS.

Causal relationship $k = 0,05822225$
P Value (one sided right tailed) (HGD) = 0,29606360
p (SINE) = 0,96875000
p (SINE) approx.= 1-(c/B) > 0,93750000
p (SINE) approx.= 1-(c/(Not A)) > 0,60000000

P VALUES.

P Value (one sided right tailed) (HGD) = 0,29606360
 $\tilde{\chi}^2$ (SINE— Not A_t) = 2,40
 $\tilde{\chi}^2$ (SINE— B_t) = 0,38
P Value (SINE) = 0,03076677

PROPORTIONS.

$(a/A) \times 100 = (90 / 177) \times 100 = 50,85 \%$
 $(b/A) \times 100 = (87 / 177) \times 100 = 49,15 \%$
 $(c/ \text{not } A) \times 100 = (6 / 15) \times 100 = 40,00 \%$
 $(d/ \text{not } A) \times 100 = (9 / 15) \times 100 = 60,00 \%$
 $(a/B) \times 100 = (90 / 96) \times 100 = 93,75 \%$
 $(c/B) \times 100 = (6 / 96) \times 100 = 6,25 \%$
 $(b/ \text{not } B) \times 100 = (87 / 96) \times 100 = 90,63 \%$
 $(d/ \text{not } B) \times 100 = (9 / 96) \times 100 = 9,38 \%$
 $(A/N) \times 100 = (177 / 192) \times 100 = 92,19 \%$
 $(\text{not } A/N) \times 100 = (15 / 192) \times 100 = 7,81 \%$
 $(B/N) \times 100 = (96 / 192) \times 100 = 50,00 \%$
 $(\text{not } B/N) \times 100 = (96 / 192) \times 100 = 50,00 \%$

ADDITIONAL STATISTICAL MEASURES.**RELATIVE RISK (RR).**

RR (necessary condition) = 1,27118644
RR (sufficient condition) = 1,03448276

OTHER STATISTICAL MEASURES.

Odds ratio (OR) = 1,55172414
Index of relationship (IOR) = 0,01694915

STUDY DESIGN.

p(IOU)= 0,42187500
p(IOI)= 0,42187500

However, the study design with p(IOU)= 0.42187500 has been very unfair even if the prevalence of CMV in the control group with $(b/ \text{not } B) \times 100 = (87 / 96) \times 100 = 90.63 \%$ has been impressive. A fair study design assumed (a=d), we would have obtained the following data.

Table 2. CMV IgG and UA (Study of Alavi et al., 2011). Fair study design.

		UA		
		YES	NO	
CMV IgG	YES	90	870	960
	NO	6	90	96
		96	960	1056

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS.

Causal relationship $k = 0,03125000$
P Value (one sided right tailed) (HGD) = 0,20716084
p (SINE) = 0,99431818
p (SINE) approx.= 1-(c/B) > 0,93750000
p (SINE) approx.= 1-(c/(Not A)) > 0,93750000

P VALUES.

P Value (one sided right tailed) (HGD) = 0,20716084
 $\tilde{\chi}^2$ (SINE— Not A_t) = 0,38
 $\tilde{\chi}^2$ (SINE— B_t) = 0,38
P Value (SINE) = 0,00566571

PROPORTIONS.

$(a/A) \times 100 = (90 / 960) \times 100 = 9,38 \%$
 $(b/A) \times 100 = (870 / 960) \times 100 = 90,63 \%$
 $(c/ \text{not } A) \times 100 = (6 / 96) \times 100 = 6,25 \%$
 $(d/ \text{not } A) \times 100 = (90 / 96) \times 100 = 93,75 \%$
 $(a/B) \times 100 = (90 / 96) \times 100 = 93,75 \%$
 $(c/B) \times 100 = (6 / 96) \times 100 = 6,25 \%$
 $(b/ \text{not } B) \times 100 = (870 / 960) \times 100 = 90,63 \%$
 $(d/ \text{not } B) \times 100 = (90 / 960) \times 100 = 9,38 \%$
 $(A/N) \times 100 = (960 / 1056) \times 100 = 90,91 \%$
 $(\text{not } A/N) \times 100 = (96 / 1056) \times 100 = 9,09 \%$
 $(B/N) \times 100 = (96 / 1056) \times 100 = 9,09 \%$
 $(\text{not } B/N) \times 100 = (960 / 1056) \times 100 = 90,91 \%$

ADDITIONAL STATISTICAL MEASURES.**RELATIVE RISK (RR).**

RR (necessary condition) = 1,50000000
RR (sufficient condition) = 1,03448276

OTHER STATISTICAL MEASURES.

Odds ratio (OR) = 1,55172414
Index of relationship (IOR) = 0,03125000

STUDY DESIGN.

p(IOU)= 0,00000000
p(IOI)= 0,81818182

In reality, the relationship between CMV and unstable angina pectoris is much stronger ($p(\text{SINE}) = 0.99431818$; P Value (SINE) = 0.00566571) than suggested by Alavi et. al.

2.2. Methods

Avoiding and treatment of logical fallacies addresses one of the most important aspects of any scientific inquiry. Sometimes logically sound definitions are of great help in order to enable us to properly infer **from something known to something unknown**. It also goes without any need of further saying that a definition as such should be logically consistent and correct. However, theoretically, circumstances might exist under which it is required to *deal with erroneous definitions*⁷ too.

2.2.1. Conditio sine qua non relationship

The probability of the necessary condition relationship $p(\text{SINE})$ has been calculated (Barukčić, 2021a,b) and tested for statistical significance. The chi-square goodness of fit test $\tilde{\chi}^2_{\text{Calculated}}(A_t \leftarrow B_t | B)$ and $\tilde{\chi}^2_{\text{Calculated}}(A_t \leftarrow B_t | \underline{A})$ with one degree of freedom has been used to test whether the sample data published fit the theoretical distribution of a necessary condition relationship in the population. Additionally, the P Value has been calculated approximately (see also Barukčić, 2019). The causal relationship k (Barukčić, 2016, 2020, 2021b) has been calculated to evaluate a possible causal relationship between the events. The cumulative, right-tailed hyper-geometric (Fisher, 1922; Gonin, 1936; Huygens and van Schooten, 1657; Pearson, 1899) distribution (HGD) has been used to test the one-sided right-tailed significance of the causal relationship k . As known, a negative causal relationship ($k < 0$) would contradict a necessary condition relationship and vice versa.

2.2.2. Hyper-geometric distribution

In general, the probability distribution of a hyper-geometric random variable X is called a hyper-geometric distribution. In contrast to the binomial distribution, the hyper-geometric distribution is characterised by the lack of replacements. In this context, let N denote the population size, let A denote the number of success in the population, let B denote the number of draws (i.e. quantity drawn in each trial), let a itself denote the number of observed successes.

Table 3. Hyper-geometric random variables

		Conditioned B_t		
		TRUE	FALSE	
Condition	TRUE	a	b	A
	A_t	FALSE	c	<u>d</u>
		B	<u>B</u>	N

With this in mind, the probability mass function of the hyper-geometric distribution (see Fisher,

⁷Strobino, Riccardo, "Ibn Sina's Logic", The Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy (Fall 2018 Edition), Edward N. Zalta (ed.), URL = <https://plato.stanford.edu/archives/fall2018/entries/ibn-sina-logic/>.

1922; Gonin, 1936; Huygens and van Schooten, 1657; Pearson, 1899), denoted as $p(X = a)$, is defined as

$$p(X = a) = \frac{\binom{A}{a} \binom{N-A}{B-a}}{\binom{N}{B}} = \frac{\binom{B}{a} \binom{N-B}{A-a}}{\binom{N}{A}} \quad (1)$$

The hyper-geometric distribution, a probability distribution of a hyper-geometric random variable, has several properties which unfortunately cannot be discussed in detail here. A cumulative hyper-geometric probability that the hyper-geometric random variable is greater than or equal to some specified lower limit a is calculated as

$$p(X \geq a) = 1 - \sum_{i=0}^{a-1} \frac{\binom{A}{i} \binom{N-A}{B-i}}{\binom{N}{B}} \quad (2)$$

A cumulative hyper-geometric probability that the hyper-geometric random variable is less than or equal to some specified upper limit a is calculated as

$$p(X \leq a) = \sum_{i=0}^a \frac{\binom{A}{i} \binom{N-A}{B-i}}{\binom{N}{B}} \quad (3)$$

2.2.3. Fisher's exact test

Fisher's exact test proposed by Fisher (1934) in the fifth edition of *Statistical Methods for Research Workers* (see Fisher, 1934, pp. 99-103) is a statistical significance test which is often used in the analysis of contingency tables while applying the hyper-geometric distribution⁸. This statistical methodology opens up the possibility to calculate the significance of the deviation from a null hypothesis (e.g., P Value) exactly. Strangely enough, it is common practice to use Fisher's exact test (see also Fisher, 1935) for a sample which is very small. However, it is necessary to point out that Fisher's exact test is valid for all sample sizes without any restriction. Fisher's Exact Test is using the following null and alternative hypotheses:

H0: (null hypothesis)

The two random variables are independent.

H1: (alternative hypothesis)

⁸Kim HY. Statistical notes for clinical researchers: Chi-squared test and Fisher's exact test. *Restor Dent Endod.* 2017 May;42(2):152-155. doi: 10.5395/rde.2017.42.2.152. Epub 2017 Mar 30. PMID: 28503482; PMCID: PMC5426219.

The two random variables are not independent.

A cumulative hyper-geometric probability denotes whether a hyper-geometric random variable is greater than or equal to some specified lower limit and less than or equal to some specified upper limit. The P Value of an one-sided right tailed Fisher's exact test is calculated as

$$p(X \geq a) = 1 - \sum_{i=0}^{i=a-1} \frac{\binom{A}{i} \binom{N-A}{B-i}}{\binom{N}{B}} \quad (4)$$

The P Value of an one-sided left tailed Fisher's exact test is calculated as

$$p(X \leq a) = \sum_{i=0}^{i=a} \frac{\binom{A}{i} \binom{N-A}{B-i}}{\binom{N}{B}} \quad (5)$$

2.2.4. The Chi-square goodness of fit test

The χ^2 distribution is one of the most versatile distributions in applied statistics. Historically, the χ^2 distribution has been described by the German statistician Friedrich Robert Helmert (see [Helmert, 1876](#)). Later, the χ^2 distribution has been rediscovered by Karl Pearson (see [Pearson, 1900](#)) in the context of a goodness of fit test. The Chi-square goodness of fit test checks the agreement or conformity or consistency between a hypothetical or a theoretical distribution given in a population and a sample distribution drawn from such a population. Karl Pearson's approximate formula for calculating a Chi-square statistic may be shown schematically as:

$$\chi^2 = \sum_{t=1}^N \frac{(\text{Observed}_t - E(\text{Observed}_t))^2}{E(\text{Observed}_t)} \quad (6)$$

Some author prefer the use of Yate's correction for continuity (see [Yates, 1934](#)) when there is one degree of freedom.

Example

Let us illustrate the Chi-square goodness of fit test by an example. A random sample of 100 people with 44 men and 56 women is drawn from a certain population. It is assumed that men and women are equal in frequency in the population. The theoretical frequencies of 50 men and 50 women is compared with the observed number of men and women.

Bernoulli trial t	Event	Observed O_t	Expected $E(O_t)$	$(O_t - E(O_t))^2$	$(O_t - E(O_t))^2 / E(O_t)$
1	Men	44	50	36	0.72
2	Women	56	50	36	0.72
Rows = 2		Sample size =	100	Chi-square =	1.44

There are rows - 1 = 2 - 1 = 1 degree of freedom and for $\alpha = 5$ percent level of significance, the rejection region is $\chi^2 \geq 3.84$. A $\chi^2 = 1.44$ is less than 3.84 and not significant. Therefore, we accept the null hypothesis: the sample distribution is consistent with a theoretical distribution given in population. In other words, men and women are more or less equal in frequency in the population. In the case of a necessary condition relationship (SINE), our hypotheses could be:

$$H_0: p(\text{SINE}) \geq 1 \text{ vs. } H_A: p(\text{SINE}) < 1$$

However, a probability cannot be greater than 1. Therefore, the hypotheses are more precisely

$$H_0: p(\text{SINE}) = 1 \text{ vs. } H_A: p(\text{SINE}) < 1$$

Accepting H_0 is equivalent with rejecting H_A and vice versa. Accepting H_A is equivalent with rejecting H_0 . Assumed that the degree of freedom is 1 and for $\alpha = 5$ percent level of significance, the rejection region is $\chi^2 \geq 3.84$. A χ^2 of a necessary condition relationship which is less than 3.84 is not significant. Therefore, we would have to accept the null hypothesis: a sample distribution would be consistent with a theoretical distribution of a necessary condition relationship given in population. However, Chi-square like any statistics has its limitations. The Chi-square is highly sensitive to sample size. The Chi-square goodness of fit test might give inaccurate results when the sample size is too small ($N < 50$) or too large (see [Bagozzi, 1981](#)) (G-square test). When the sample sizes are too small, Fisher's exact test of independence can be considered too.

3. Results

3.1. The relationship between CMV IgG and UA

Theorem 1 (Without CMV IgG no UA).

In order for event A_t to be the cause of another event B_t , an event A_t must be at least a necessary condition of event B_t . If event B_t can occur without the existence of event A_t , then A_t cannot be the cause of event B_t either. This elementary relationship allows us to approach the causal relation between events A_t and B_t from a different point of view. Our hypothesis is as follows.

Claim.

Null-hypothesis: Without CMV IgG no UA is true.

Alternative hypothesis: Without CMV IgG no UA is false.

PROOF BY INDUCTION.

Whether CMV IgG could be a necessary condition of UA has been examined by the data of Seyed Mohammad Alavi et al.⁹ (see table 1).

The study design with $p(\text{IOU}) = 0.42187500$ has been very unfair, even if the prevalence of CMV in the control group with $(b/\text{not } B) \times 100 = (87 / 96) \times 100 = 90.63\%$ was acceptable. Nevertheless, despite several and obviously massive disadvantages, it was possible to prove that the relationship without CMV IgG positivity no unstable angina pectoris ($p(\text{SINE}) = 0.96875000$; P Value (SINE) = 0.03076677) is true.

END PROOF BY INDUCTION.

⁹Alavi SM, Adel SM, Rajabzadeh AR. An evidence against the effect of chronic cytomegalovirus infection in unstable angina pectoris. *Acta Med Iran.* 2011;49(2):78-80. PMID: 21598213.

4. Discussion

In contrast to the conclusion drawn, the data published by Alavi et al.¹⁰ provided convincing evidence of the relationship between CMV-IgG seropositivity and unstable angina. These data are in accordance with various others studies^{11, 12, 13, 14} CMV is a member of the herpesviruses and a double-stranded DNA virus. Unfortunately, after recovery of the primary infection, CMV remains dormant within the host. No wonder, the CMV seroprevalence is increasing with age. When reactivation occurs, virions are released into the bloodstream and other body fluids, leading to the presence of various symptoms. Cytomegalovirus (CMV) infections are associated with increased morbidity and mortality and poses a major challenge for patient and physicians. Thus far, several antiviral agents like cidofovir, foscarnet, ganciclovir, valganciclovir et cetera have been proposed for the treatment of CMV. Even leflunomide seems to have some effect against CMV. Leflunomide or (N-(4'-trifluoromethylphenyl)-5-methylisoxazole-4-carboxamide) is an inhibitor of protein kinase activity and pyrimidine synthesis and is easily given orally. Leflunomide works more or less by inhibiting virion assembly.^{15 16} Various authors were able to provide some evidence that leflunomide is potentially effective^{17 18} against cases

¹⁰Alavi SM, Adel SM, Rajabzadeh AR. An evidence against the effect of chronic cytomegalovirus infection in unstable angina pectoris. *Acta Med Iran.* 2011;49(2):78-80. PMID: 21598213.

¹¹Barukčić, Ilija. (2020). Human cytomegalovirus is the cause of human atherosclerosis. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3902775>

¹²Gabrylewicz B, Mazurek U, Ochała A, Sliupkas-Dyrda E, Garbocz P, Pyrlík A, Mróz I, Wilczok T, Tendera M. Cytomegalovirus infection in acute myocardial infarction. Is there a causative relationship? *Kardiol Pol.* 2003 Oct;59(10):283-92. PMID: 14618212.

¹³Huang ZR, Yu LP, Yang XC, Zhang F, Chen YR, Feng F, Qian XS, Cai J. Human cytomegalovirus linked to stroke in a Chinese population. *CNS Neurosci Ther.* 2012 Jun;18(6):457-60. doi: 10.1111/j.1755-5949.2012.00326.x. PMID: 22672297; PMCID: PMC6493519.

¹⁴Mundkur LA, Rao VS, Hebbagudi S, Shanker J, Shivanandan H, Nagaraj RK, Kakkar VV. Pathogen burden, cytomegalovirus infection and inflammatory markers in the risk of premature coronary artery disease in individuals of Indian origin. *Exp Clin Cardiol.* 2012 Summer;17(2):63-8. PMID: 22826649; PMCID: PMC3395457.

¹⁵Waldman WJ, Knight DA, Blinder L, Shen J, Lurain NS, Miller DM, Sedmak DD, Williams JW, Chong AS. Inhibition of cytomegalovirus in vitro and in vivo by the experimental immunosuppressive agent leflunomide. *Intervirology.* 1999;42(5-6):412-8. doi: 10.1159/000053979. PMID: 10702725.

¹⁶Waldman WJ, Knight DA, Lurain NS, Miller DM, Sedmak DD, Williams JW, Chong AS. Novel mechanism of inhibition of cytomegalovirus by the experimental immunosuppressive agent leflunomide. *Transplantation.* 1999 Sep 27;68(6):814-25. doi: 10.1097/00007890-199909270-00014. PMID: 10515382.

¹⁷John GT, Manivannan J, Chandy S, Peter S, Jacob CK. Leflunomide therapy for cytomegalovirus disease in renal allograft recipients. *Transplantation.* 2004 May 15;77(9):1460-1. doi: 10.1097/01.tp.0000122185.64004.89. PMID: 15167608.

¹⁸Avery RK, Bolwell BJ, Yen-Lieberman B, Lurain N, Waldman WJ, Longworth DL, Taeye AJ, Mossad SB, Kohn D, Long JR, Curtis J, Kalaycio M, Pohlman B, Williams JW. Use of leflunomide in an allogeneic bone marrow transplant recipient with refractory cytomegalovirus infection. *Bone Marrow Transplant.* 2004 Dec;34(12):1071-5. doi: 10.1038/sj.bmt.1704694. PMID: 15489872.

of CMV infection too. [19](#) , [20](#) , [21](#) , [22](#) , [23](#) , [24](#) , [25](#) , [26](#) , [27](#) , [28](#) , [29](#)

5. Conclusion

Based on the data of Alavi et al., the following conclusion is logically inevitable.

‘Without CMV infection, no unstable angina pectoris.’

Acknowledgments

No funding or any financial support by a third party was received.

Erratum

Unfortunately, some misprints appeared in the previous publications, especially in the section of definitions. Some of the misprints have been brought up to date in this publication as far as possible.

¹⁹Sudarsanam TD, Sahni RD, John GT. Leflunomide: a possible alternative for ganciclovir sensitive and resistant cytomegalovirus infections. *Postgrad Med J.* 2006 May;82(967):313-4. doi: 10.1136/pgmj.2005.038521. PMID: 16679469; PMCID: PMC2563786.

²⁰John GT, Manivannan J, Chandu S, Peter S, Jacob CK. Leflunomide therapy for cytomegalovirus disease in renal allograft recipients. *Transplantation.* 2004 May 15;77(9):1460-1. doi: 10.1097/01.tp.0000122185.64004.89. PMID: 15167608.

²¹Suissa S, Bernatsky S, Hudson M. Antirheumatic drug use and the risk of acute myocardial infarction. *Arthritis Rheum.* 2006 Aug 15;55(4):531-6. doi: 10.1002/art.22094. PMID: 16874796.

²²Kaur H, Sarma P, Bhattacharyya A, Sharma S, Chhimpa N, Prajapat M, Prakash A, Kumar S, Singh A, Singh R, Avti P, Thota P, Medhi B. Efficacy and safety of dihydroorotate dehydrogenase (DHODH) inhibitors "leflunomide" and "teriflunomide" in Covid-19: A narrative review. *Eur J Pharmacol.* 2021 Sep 5;906:174233. doi: 10.1016/j.ejphar.2021.174233. Epub 2021 Jun 7. PMID: 34111397; PMCID: PMC8180448.

²³Su N, Liu Z, Sun P, Gu F, Yan X, Cai D. Donor-derived cytomegalovirus-cytotoxic T lymphocytes and leflunomide successfully control refractory cytomegalovirus infections and disease of multiple sites after allogeneic-hematopoietic stem cell transplantation: A case report. *Front Med (Lausanne).* 2022 Sep 6;9:948210. doi: 10.3389/fmed.2022.948210. PMID: 36148446; PMCID: PMC9485495.

²⁴Tan BH. Cytomegalovirus Treatment. *Curr Treat Options Infect Dis.* 2014;6(3):256-270. doi: 10.1007/s40506-014-0021-5. PMID: 25999800; PMCID: PMC4431713.

²⁵Gokarn A, Toshniwal A, Pathak A, Arora S, Bonda A, Punatar S, Nayak L, Dwivedi P, Bhat V, Biswas S, Kelkar R, Kannan S, Khattry N. Use of Leflunomide for Treatment of Cytomegalovirus Infection in Recipients of Allogeneic Stem Cell Transplant. *Biol Blood Marrow Transplant.* 2019 Sep;25(9):1832-1836. doi: 10.1016/j.bbmt.2019.04.028. Epub 2019 May 2. PMID: 31054984.

²⁶Bilger A, Plowshay J, Ma S, Nawandar D, Barlow EA, Romero-Masters JC, Bristol JA, Li Z, Tsai MH, Delecluse HJ, Kenney SC. Leflunomide/teriflunomide inhibit Epstein-Barr virus (EBV)- induced lymphoproliferative disease and lytic viral replication. *Oncotarget.* 2017 Jul 4;8(27):44266-44280. doi: 10.18632/oncotarget.17863. PMID: 28574826; PMCID: PMC5546479.

²⁷Qi R, Hua-Song Z, Xiao-Feng Z. Leflunomide inhibits the apoptosis of human embryonic lung fibroblasts infected by human cytomegalovirus. *Eur J Med Res.* 2013 Feb 1;18(1):3. doi: 10.1186/2047-783X-18-3. PMID: 23369524; PMCID: PMC3598351.

²⁸Chong AS, Zeng H, Knight DA, Shen J, Meister GT, Williams JW, Waldman WJ. Concurrent antiviral and immunosuppressive activities of leflunomide in vivo. *Am J Transplant.* 2006 Jan;6(1):69-75. doi: 10.1111/j.1600-6143.2005.01152.x. PMID: 16433758.

²⁹Barukčić, Ilija. (2023). Leflunomide is effective against acute myocardial infarction. *Causation*, 19(7), 5–28. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7771871>

Private note

The definition section of a paper need not and does not necessarily contain new scientific aspects. Above all, it also serves to better understand a scientific publication, to follow every step of the arguments of an author and to explain in greater details the fundamentals on which a publication is based. Therefore, there is no objective need to force authors to reinvent a scientific wheel once and again unless such a need appears obviously factually necessary. The effort to write about a certain subject in an original way in multiple publications does not exclude the necessity simply to cut and paste from an earlier work, and has nothing to do with self-plagiarism. However, such an attitude cannot simply be transferred to the sections' introduction, results, discussion and conclusions et cetera.

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I was born October, 1st 1961 in Novo Selo, Bosnia and Herzegovina, former Yugoslavia. I am of Croatian origin. From 1982-1989 C.E., I studied human medicine at the University of Hamburg, Germany. Meanwhile, I am working as a specialist of internal medicine. My basic field of research since my high school days at the Wirtschaftsgymnasium Bruchsal, Baden Württemberg, Germany is the mathematization of the relationship between a cause and an effect valid without any restriction under any circumstances including the conditions of classical logic, probability theory, quantum mechanics, special and general theory of relativity, human medicine et cetera. I endeavour to investigate positions of quantum mechanics, relativity theory, mathematics et cetera, only insofar as these positions put into question or endanger **the general validity of the principle of causality**.

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